

Supplementary Tables and Figures

for

Skyline fossilized birth-death model is robust to violations of sampling assumptions in total-evidence dating

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Table S1: Fossil ages used in the Hymenoptera analyses. Only the mean values were used, the ranges from O'Reilly and Donoghue (2016) are for reference.

Fossil	Age (mean and range)		
Triassoxyela	231 (226.4, 236)		
Asioxyela	231 (226.4, 236)	Ghilarella	138 (119.6, 156.76)
Nigrimonticola	159 (151.2, 168)	Paroryssus	159 (151.2, 168)
Gigantoxyelinae	116 (104, 128.6)	Praeoryssus	159 (151.2, 168)
Spathoxyela	116 (104, 128.6)	Mesorussus	103 (77.63, 128.6)
Xyela mesozoica	116 (104, 128.6)	Trematothorax	116 (104, 128.6)
Angaridyela	116 (104, 128.6)	Thoracotrema	138 (119.6, 156.76)
Xyelotoma	159 (151.2, 168)	Prosyntexis	79 (71.9, 86.8)
Undatoma	106 (65.9, 145.8)	Kulbastavia	159 (151.2, 168)
Dahuratoma	102 (71.9, 131.3)	Brachysyntexis	159 (151.2, 168)
Mesolyda	159 (151.2, 168)	Symphytopterus	159 (151.2, 168)
Turgidontes	102 (71.9, 131.3)	Eoxyela	155 (141, 168)
Aulidontes	159 (151.2, 168)	Liadoxyela	155 (141, 168)
Protosirex	159 (151.2, 168)	Abrotoxyela	163 (157.4, 168)
Aulisca	159 (151.2, 168)	Pseudoxyelocerus	181 (179.66, 182.4)
Anaxyela	159 (151.2, 168)	Palaeathalia	116 (104, 128.6)
Syntexyela	159 (151.2, 168)	Ferganolyda	170 (156.3, 183.4)
Karatavites	159 (151.2, 168)	Pamphiliidae undesc	163 (157.4, 168)
Stephanogaster	159 (151.2, 168)	Rudisiricius	163 (157.4, 168)
Leptephialtites	159 (151.2, 168)	Sogutia	162 (157.4, 167.3)
Cleistogaster	155 (141, 168)	Xyelula	181 (179.66, 182.4)
Sepulca	159 (151.2, 168)	Brigittepterus	181 (179.66, 182.4)
Onochoius	102 (71.9, 131.3)	Grimmaratavites	181 (179.66, 182.4)

Table S2: Fossil ages used in the Eutheria analyses, taken from Ronquist et al. (2016).

Fossil	Age
<i>Eomaia scansoria</i>	123.3
<i>Maelestes gobiensis</i>	77.8
<i>Metacheiromys marshi</i>	48.2
<i>Ukhaatherium nessovi</i>	77.8
<i>Zalambdalestes lechei</i>	77.8
<i>Leptictis dakotensis</i>	35.3
<i>Moeritherium lyonsi</i>	35.5
<i>Notharctus tenebrosus</i>	48.2
<i>Protungulatum donnae</i>	64.6
<i>Apheliscus insidiosus</i>	53.0
<i>Phenacodus intermedius</i>	56.2
<i>Protolipterna ellipsodontoides</i>	58.2
<i>Hyopsodus paulus</i>	48.3
<i>Didolodus multicuspis</i>	52.5
<i>Carodnia vieirai</i>	58.2
<i>Thomashuxleya externa</i>	52.5
<i>Vulpavus ovatus</i>	48.3
<i>Vulpavus profectus</i>	48.3
<i>Sinopa rapax</i>	48.3
<i>Dawsonolagus antiquus</i>	53.5
<i>Gomphos elkema</i>	55.5
<i>Rhombomylus turpanensis</i>	53.5
<i>Tribosphenomys minutus</i>	58.0
<i>Paramys delicatus</i>	52.8
<i>Cocomys lingchaensis</i>	55.5
<i>Mesohippus bairdi</i>	36.0
<i>Basilosaurus cetoides</i>	38.7
<i>Mesonyx obtusidens</i>	48.0
<i>Archaeotherium mortoni</i>	36.0
<i>Artiocetus clavis</i>	47.0
<i>Rodhocetus balochistanensis</i>	47.0
<i>Icaronycteris index</i>	52.2
<i>Onychonycteris finneyi</i>	52.2

Table S3: Key parameter estimates between BEAST 2 and MrBayes 3.2 (median and 95% HPD CI) under strict clock and constant-rate FBD model. The α 's are for gamma rate variations across characters, m 's are for partition rate multipliers among the seven partitions, and c is the clock rate.

Parameter	BEAST 2	MrBayes 3.2	BEAST 2	MrBayes 3.2
	Diversified sampling		Random sampling	
$d = \lambda - \mu$	0.0069 (0.0042, 0.010)	0.0075 (0.0043, 0.011)	0.0069 (0.0048, 0.0093)	0.0070 (0.0048, 0.0094)
$r = \mu / \lambda$	0.9994 (0.999, 0.9996)	0.9993 (0.999, 0.9996)	0.9975 (0.9953, 0.9988)	0.9977 (0.9957, 0.9989)
$s = \psi / (\mu + \psi)$	1E-6 (1E-6, 1E-6)	1E-6 (1E-6, 1E-6)	2E-6 (1E-6, 3.6E-6)	2E-6 (1E-6, 3E-6)
t_{root}	468.5 (407.7, 531.4)	455.6 (380.8, 519.9)	562.2 (469.8, 674.7)	544.5 (465.2, 649.6)
$t_{\text{Hymenoptera}}$	373.4 (330.6, 425.6)	362.8 (304.4, 415.6)	445.4 (375.0, 537.4)	430.8 (365.0, 514.8)
c_{strict}	6.9E-4 (6.0E-4, 7.9E-4)	7.3E-4 (6.3E-4, 8.6E-4)	6.2E-4 (5.0E-4, 7.3E-4)	6.5E-4 (5.4E-4, 7.6E-4)
α_{morph}	1.81 (1.44, 2.24)	1.84 (1.43, 2.28)	1.80 (1.44, 2.22)	1.86 (1.45, 2.30)
α_2	0.46 (0.39, 0.53)	0.51 (0.44, 0.58)	0.46 (0.39, 0.53)	0.50 (0.44, 0.57)
α_3	0.18 (0.16, 0.21)	0.21 (0.18, 0.24)	0.18 (0.16, 0.21)	0.21 (0.18, 0.24)
α_4	0.20 (0.17, 0.23)	0.22 (0.19, 0.26)	0.20 (0.17, 0.23)	0.22 (0.19, 0.26)
α_5	0.27 (0.24, 0.29)	0.29 (0.26, 0.32)	0.26 (0.24, 0.29)	0.29 (0.26, 0.32)
α_6	0.13 (0.12, 0.14)	0.14 (0.13, 0.16)	0.13 (0.12, 0.14)	0.14 (0.13, 0.16)
α_7	0.95 (0.85, 1.06)	0.99 (0.88, 1.10)	0.89 (0.80, 0.99)	0.91 (0.82, 1.02)
m_1	1.15 (1.04, 1.27)	1.11 (0.99, 1.22)	1.10 (0.99, 1.22)	1.06 (0.95, 1.17)
m_2	1.02 (0.90, 1.13)	1.03 (0.92, 1.15)	0.98 (0.87, 1.10)	1.00 (0.88, 1.11)
m_3	0.16 (0.14, 0.19)	0.16 (0.13, 0.18)	0.15 (0.13, 0.18)	0.15 (0.13, 0.17)
m_4	0.25 (0.21, 0.29)	0.25 (0.21, 0.29)	0.24 (0.20, 0.28)	0.24 (0.20, 0.28)
m_5	0.80 (0.73, 0.86)	0.77 (0.71, 0.83)	0.76 (0.70, 0.83)	0.74 (0.68, 0.80)
m_6	0.21 (0.19, 0.24)	0.20 (0.18, 0.23)	0.20 (0.18, 0.23)	0.19 (0.17, 0.22)
m_7	4.28 (4.13, 4.43)	4.34 (4.20, 4.49)	4.39 (4.24, 4.55)	4.46 (4.31, 4.61)

Table S4: Key parameter estimates between BEAST 2 and MrBayes 3.2 (median and 95% HPD CI) under UCLD relaxed clock and constant-rate FBD model. The α 's are for gamma rate variations across characters, m 's are for partition rate multipliers among the seven partitions, c is the mean clock rate, and σ is the clock standard deviation.

Parameter	BEAST 2	MrBayes 3.2	BEAST 2	MrBayes 3.2
	Diversified sampling		Random sampling	
$d = \lambda - \mu$	0.010 (0.0062, 0.014)	0.010 (0.0063, 0.014)	0.0089 (0.0059, 0.012)	0.0089 (0.0058, 0.012)
$r = \mu / \lambda$	0.999 (0.9984, 0.9995)	0.9989 (0.998, 0.9994)	0.9980 (0.9965, 0.9991)	0.9981 (0.9966, 0.9990)
$s = \psi / (\mu + \psi)$	1E-6 (1E-6, 2E-6)	1E-6 (1E-6, 2E-6)	1E-6 (1E-6, 3E-6)	1E-6 (1E-6, 3E-6)
t_{root}	341.0 (315.0, 387.7)	336.2 (315.0, 377.4)	409.4 (331.6, 511.8)	403.9 (330.6, 498.4)
$t_{\text{Hymenoptera}}$	294.9 (263.8, 330.8)	296.9 (269.2, 334.3)	345.4 (287.5, 426.1)	345.9 (289.2, 419.2)
c_{uclid}	1.2E-3 (9.4E-4, 1.4E-3)	1.2E-3 (9.4E-4, 1.4E-3)	9.5E-4 (7.2E-4, 1.2E-3)	9.7E-4 (7.5E-4, 1.2E-3)
σ_{uclid}	0.78 (0.67, 0.91)	0.91 (0.55, 1.36)	0.54 (0.45, 0.65)	0.39 (0.24, 0.59)
α_{morph}	1.78 (1.42, 2.19)	1.77 (1.38, 2.20)	1.79 (1.41, 2.20)	1.79 (1.39, 2.21)
α_2	0.46 (0.40, 0.54)	0.51 (0.45, 0.58)	0.46 (0.40, 0.54)	0.51 (0.44, 0.58)
α_3	0.18 (0.16, 0.21)	0.21 (0.18, 0.24)	0.18 (0.16, 0.21)	0.21 (0.18, 0.24)
α_4	0.19 (0.16, 0.23)	0.22 (0.18, 0.26)	0.19 (0.17, 0.23)	0.22 (0.19, 0.26)
α_5	0.27 (0.24, 0.30)	0.29 (0.26, 0.32)	0.27 (0.24, 0.30)	0.29 (0.26, 0.32)
α_6	0.13 (0.12, 0.14)	0.14 (0.13, 0.16)	0.13 (0.12, 0.14)	0.14 (0.13, 0.16)
α_7	0.89 (0.79, 0.99)	0.91 (0.82, 1.02)	0.89 (0.79, 0.98)	0.91 (0.81, 1.02)
m_1	1.07 (0.96, 1.18)	1.03 (0.93, 1.14)	1.06 (0.96, 1.18)	1.02 (0.92, 1.13)
m_2	0.96 (0.87, 1.07)	0.96 (0.86, 1.07)	0.96 (0.86, 1.07)	0.96 (0.86, 1.07)
m_3	0.15 (0.13, 0.17)	0.15 (0.13, 0.17)	0.15 (0.13, 0.17)	0.15 (0.13, 0.17)
m_4	0.23 (0.20, 0.27)	0.23 (0.19, 0.27)	0.23 (0.19, 0.27)	0.23 (0.19, 0.27)
m_5	0.76 (0.69, 0.82)	0.73 (0.67, 0.79)	0.76 (0.69, 0.82)	0.73 (0.67, 0.79)
m_6	0.21 (0.18, 0.23)	0.20 (0.18, 0.22)	0.21 (0.18, 0.23)	0.20 (0.17, 0.22)
m_7	4.43 (4.28, 4.58)	4.50 (4.34, 4.65)	4.43 (4.28, 4.58)	4.50 (4.34, 4.65)

We note a slight difference in the age estimates under the UCLD relaxed clock and diversified-sampling FBD models comparing with the results in Zhang et al. (2016, cf. Table 5, e.g., median age of Hymenoptera was 279.4 Ma, about 15 Myr younger). Three main factors can contribute to this. One is that they used the white noise relaxed clock model (Lepage et al. 2007) in MrBayes. Another is the presence of the Holometabola calibration in their study. We removed that calibration to focus on the utility of the SFBD priors themselves. The third is that several fossil ages have been updated according to O'Reilly and Donoghue (2016).

Table S5: Key parameter estimates between BEAST 2 and MrBayes 3.2 (median and 95% HPD CI) under UCLD relaxed clock and ten-interval SFBD model.

Parameter	BEAST 2	MrBayes 3.2	BEAST 2	MrBayes 3.2
	Diversified sampling		Random sampling	
$d_1 = \lambda_1 - \mu_1$	0.0097 (5E-5, 0.030)	0.011 (1E-4, 0.033)	0.0097 (3E-5, 0.031)	0.010 (3E-5, 0.033)
d_2	0.017 (4E-6, 0.049)	0.017 (1E-6, 0.048)	0.016 (2E-6, 0.049)	0.016 (5E-6, 0.048)
d_3	0.028 (1E-3, 0.060)	0.026 (2E-3, 0.057)	0.027 (2E-3, 0.060)	0.026 (2E-3, 0.057)
d_4	0.029 (5E-6, 0.060)	0.025 (2E-6, 0.052)	0.030 (1E-3, 0.061)	0.025 (9E-4, 0.052)
d_5	0.029 (3E-3, 0.056)	0.026 (3E-3, 0.052)	0.030 (4E-3, 0.059)	0.028 (4E-3, 0.055)
d_6	0.0043 (1E-4, 0.013)	0.005 (4E-4, 0.013)	0.0047 (4E-4, 0.013)	0.0048 (3E-4, 0.013)
d_7	0.011 (5E-5, 0.029)	0.012 (3E-4, 0.031)	0.0099 (7E-5, 0.027)	0.011 (2E-4, 0.028)
d_8	0.016 (8E-5, 0.040)	0.019 (4E-5, 0.046)	0.012 (2E-5, 0.032)	0.013 (2E-6, 0.032)
d_9	0.051 (3E-3, 0.102)	0.064 (1E-6, 0.114)	0.028 (1E-6, 0.058)	0.030 (2E-3, 0.063)
d_{10}	0.10 (0.05, 0.15)	0.091 (0.04, 0.14)	0.12 (0.09, 0.15)	0.12 (0.10, 0.15)
$r_1 = \mu_1 / \lambda_1$	0.20 (3E-6, 0.70)	0.20 (5E-6, 0.71)	0.21 (8E-6, 0.72)	0.21 (4E-6, 0.71)
r_2	0.19 (9E-6, 0.70)	0.19 (4E-6, 0.70)	0.20 (2E-7, 0.70)	0.20 (0E-6, 0.71)
r_3	0.28 (2E-3, 0.76)	0.28 (4E-3, 0.74)	0.30 (5E-3, 0.77)	0.29 (4E-3, 0.75)
r_4	0.11 (3E-6, 0.62)	0.12 (0E-6, 0.61)	0.12 (3E-6, 0.65)	0.12 (1E-6, 0.63)
r_5	0.26 (4E-3, 0.69)	0.25 (9E-3, 0.69)	0.29 (0.01, 0.76)	0.24 (0.006, 0.67)
r_6	0.93 (0.74, 1.00)	0.88 (0.58, 0.99)	0.93 (0.72, 0.99)	0.89 (0.60, 0.99)
r_7	0.40 (0.02, 0.84)	0.38 (0.02, 0.84)	0.42 (0.02, 0.87)	0.41 (0.02, 0.84)
r_8	0.50 (3E-4, 0.91)	0.33 (3E-4, 0.85)	0.45 (5E-4, 0.90)	0.36 (5E-4, 0.87)
r_9	0.08 (1E-8, 0.75)	0.04 (0E-6, 0.64)	0.20 (8E-7, 0.87)	0.12 (3E-6, 0.74)
r_{10}	0.96 (0.80, 0.99)	0.97 (0.82, 0.99)	0.004 (1E-8, 0.40)	0.003 (1E-6, 0.37)
$s_1 = \psi_1 / (\mu_1 + \psi_1)$	0.24 (9E-8, 0.75)	0.24 (9E-6, 0.75)	0.26 (8E-6, 0.76)	0.25 (6E-5, 0.76)
s_2	0.23 (2E-5, 0.74)	0.23 (7E-6, 0.75)	0.23 (1E-6, 0.75)	0.23 (2E-5, 0.74)
s_3	0.30 (0.02, 0.77)	0.32 (0.02, 0.77)	0.31 (0.02, 0.76)	0.33 (0.02, 0.79)
s_4	0.10 (2E-7, 0.59)	0.12 (6E-6, 0.61)	0.10 (3E-6, 0.59)	0.12 (3E-6, 0.60)
s_5	0.25 (0.02, 0.72)	0.33 (0.04, 0.76)	0.23 (0.01, 0.70)	0.34 (0.05, 0.77)
s_6	0.09 (0.01, 0.28)	0.16 (0.02, 0.47)	0.10 (0.01, 0.30)	0.17 (0.03, 0.48)
s_7	0.30 (0.01, 0.76)	0.30 (0.03, 0.76)	0.31 (0.02, 0.78)	0.33 (0.03, 0.79)
s_8	0.02 (1E-5, 0.38)	0.03 (4E-5, 0.45)	0.03 (6E-5, 0.45)	0.048 (5E-5, 0.52)
s_9	0.009 (7E-8, 0.37)	0.011 (3E-6, 0.38)	0.009 (5E-8, 0.37)	0.016 (1E-6, 0.40)
s_{10}	5E-5 (1E-8, 2E-3)	1E-5 (1E-6, 1E-3)	0.002 (1E-8, 0.30)	0.003 (1E-6, 0.28)
t_{root}	356.2 (315.0, 424.3)	341.1 (315.0, 429.1)	338.7 (315.0, 413.4)	339.8 (315.0, 401.6)
$t_{\text{Hymenoptera}}$	297.1 (246.9, 350.8)	289.0 (242.4, 352.7)	278.6 (236.5, 338.8)	284.8 (243.3, 335.5)
c_{uclD}	1.1E-3 (9.1E-4, 1.4E-3)	1.2E-3 (9.0E-4, 1.5E-3)	1.2E-3 (9.2E-4, 1.5E-3)	1.2E-3 (9.5E-4, 1.5E-3)
σ_{uclD}	0.65 (0.54, 0.77)	0.60 (0.35, 0.92)	0.60 (0.49, 0.73)	0.52 (0.30, 0.79)

Figure S1: Simulated trajectories from the OU process (500 replicates). Parameter values are drawn from the specified distributions shown in the figure. The thick (red) lines represent the median and the 95% HPD CI. Note that the trajectories are not restricted to be positive.

Figure S2. Relative CI widths for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1, (Inferences 1–4). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates (i.e., for 200 trees). Input trees were fixed to the true trees simulated under random sampling (rnd), with sampling assumptions matched between simulation and inference.

Figure S3. Relative CI widths for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1, (Inferences 5–8). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates (i.e., for 200 trees). Input trees were fixed to the true trees simulated under random sampling (rnd), but sampling assumptions were mismatched between simulation and inference.

Figure S4. Relative CI widths for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1, (Inferences 9–12). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates (i.e., for 200 trees). Input trees were fixed to the true trees simulated under diversified sampling (div), with sampling assumptions matched between simulation and inference.

Figure S5. Relative CI widths for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1, (Inferences 13–16). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates (i.e., for 200 trees). Input trees were fixed to the true trees simulated under diversified sampling (div), but sampling assumptions were mismatched between simulation and inference.

Figure S6: Posterior medians for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 1–4). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under strict clock given trees sampled under random sampling (rnd), with sampling assumptions matched between simulation and inference. The dotted horizontal line represents the true value of the parameter.

Figure S7: Relative CI widths for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 1–4). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under strict clock given trees sampled under random sampling (rnd), with sampling assumptions matched between simulation and inference.

Figure S8: Posterior medians for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 5–8). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under strict clock given trees sampled under random sampling (rnd), but sampling assumptions were mismatched between simulation and inference. The dotted horizontal line represents the true value of the parameter.

Figure S9: Relative CI widths for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 5–8). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under strict clock given trees sampled under random sampling (rnd), but sampling assumptions were mismatched between simulation and inference.

Figure S10: Posterior medians for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 9–12). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under strict clock given trees sampled under diversified sampling (div), with sampling assumptions matched between simulation and inference. The dotted horizontal line represents the true value of the parameter.

Figure S11: Relative CI widths for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 9–12). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under strict clock given trees sampled under diversified sampling (div), with sampling assumptions matched between simulation and inference.

Figure S12: Posterior medians for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 13–16). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under strict clock given trees sampled under diversified sampling (div), but sampling assumptions were mismatched between simulation and inference. The dotted horizontal line represents the true value of the parameter.

Figure S13: Relative CI widths for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 13–16). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under strict clock given trees sampled under diversified sampling (div), but sampling assumptions were mismatched between simulation and inference.

Figure S14: Posterior medians for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 1–4). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under UCLD relaxed clock given trees sampled under random sampling (rnd), with sampling assumptions matched between simulation and inference. The dotted horizontal line represents the true value of the parameter.

Figure S15: Relative CI widths for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 1–4). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under UCLD relaxed clock given trees sampled under random sampling (rnd), with sampling assumptions matched between simulation and inference.

Figure S16: Posterior medians for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 5–8). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under UCLD relaxed clock given trees sampled under random sampling (*rnd*), but sampling assumptions were mismatched between simulation and inference. The dotted horizontal line represents the true value of the parameter.

Figure S17: Relative CI widths for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 5–8). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under UCLD relaxed clock given trees sampled under random sampling (rnd), but sampling assumptions were mismatched between simulation and inference.

Figure S18: Posterior medians for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 9–12). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under UCLD relaxed clock given trees sampled under diversified sampling (div), with sampling assumptions matched between simulation and inference. The dotted horizontal line represents the true value of the parameter.

Figure S19: Relative CI widths for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 9–12). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under UCLD relaxed clock given trees sampled under diversified sampling (div), with sampling assumptions matched between simulation and inference.

Figure S20: Posterior medians for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 13–16). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under UCLD relaxed clock given trees sampled under diversified sampling (div), but sampling assumptions were mismatched between simulation and inference. The dotted horizontal line represents the true value of the parameter.

Figure S21: Relative CI widths for the SFBD rates under various conditions in Table 1 (Inferences 13–16). Each violin plot summarizes the values across 200 replicates. Morphological matrices were simulated under UCLD relaxed clock given trees sampled under diversified sampling (div), but sampling assumptions were mismatched between simulation and inference.

Figure S22. Maximum clade credibility (MCC) tree from the Hymenoptera analysis under diversified-sampling SFBD model with 10 i.i.d. intervals (Table 2, case 4). The five representative nodes for Fig. 8 are marked. The MCC trees under different prior settings can be found in Supplementary Material (NEXUS files).

Figure S23. The SFBD rates (median and 95% CI) sampled without morphological and molecular data under diversified sampling in the Hymenoptera analyses, using the SFBD model settings shown in Table 2 (Inferences 3–7). Fossil ages were used same as in the standard analyses (Fig. 9).

Figure S24. The SFBD rates (median and 95% CI) sampled without morphological and molecular data under random sampling in the Hymenoptera analyses, using the SFBD model settings shown in Table 2 (Inferences 3–7). Fossil ages were used same as in the standard analyses (Fig. 10).

Figure S25: In the Hymenoptera analyses, a) Posterior estimates of five representative node ages (Ma, median and 95% HPD CI) under the diversified-sampling SFBD model with $\rho = 0.001$ (circle and gray) and $\rho = 0.1$ (square and black). b) Posterior estimates of the SFBD rates (median and 95% HPD CI) under diversified sampling with $\rho = 0.1$ (Table 2, 4b & 6b). c) Posterior estimates of the SFBD rates (median and 95% HPD CI) under diversified sampling with $\rho = 0.1$ and under random sampling with $\rho = 0.001$. Different from the main results using the OU prior with 20 intervals (Figs 9&10), the Gamma(4, 0.2) distribution was used for σ instead of Gamma(4, 0.005).

Figure S26. Maximum clade credibility (MCC) tree from the Eutheria analysis under diversified-sampling SFBD model with 10 i.i.d. intervals (Table 2, case 4). The five representative nodes for Fig. 11 are marked. The MCC trees under different prior settings can be found in Supplementary Material (NEXUS files).

Figure S27. The SFBD rates (median and 95% CI) sampled without morphological and molecular data under diversified sampling in the Eutheria analyses, using the SFBD model settings shown in Table 2 (Inferences 3–7). Fossil ages were used same as in the standard analyses (Fig. 12).

Figure S28. The SFBD rates (median and 95% CI) sampled without morphological and molecular data under random sampling in the Eutheria analyses, using the SFBD model settings shown in Table 2 (Inferences 3–7). Fossil ages were used same as in the standard analyses (Fig. 13).

Figure S29: In the Eutheria analyses, a) Posterior estimates of five representative node ages (Ma, median and 95% HPD CI) under the diversified-sampling SFBD model with $\rho = 0.01$ (circle and gray) and $\rho = 0.2$ (square and black). b) Posterior estimates of the SFBD rates (median and 95% HPD CI) under diversified sampling with $\rho = 0.2$ (Table 2, 4b & 6b). c) Posterior estimates of the SFBD rates (median and 95% HPD CI) under diversified sampling with $\rho = 0.2$ and under random sampling with $\rho = 0.01$. Different from the main results using the OU prior with 20 intervals (Figs 12&13), the Gamma(4, 0.2) distribution was used for σ instead of Gamma(4, 0.005).